

STUDIES IN DEHYDROGENATION PART IV.

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In the present communication the syntheses of 7-methyl- and 7-ethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spirocyclopentane have been described and the selenium dehydrogenation of these two spiro-hydrocarbons has been studied.

Interesting results were obtained when spiro-hydrocarbons were subjected to selenium dehydrogenation. It has been shown in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 389) that tetrahydronaphthalene-spirocyclopentane (VII ; R=H) undergoes ring transformation when heated with selenium, with the formation of both anthracene and phenanthrene. Now it has been found that 7-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spiro-cyclopentane (VII ; R=Me) gives on dehydrogenation with selenium both 3-methylphenanthrene and β -methylantracene, while 7-ethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2 : 2-spirocyclopentane (VII ; R=Et) yields 3-ethylphenanthrene and probably β -ethylanthracene. The cyclopentane ring is not dehydrogenated till it opens up and is transformed into a six-membered ring. In all cases, studied so far, it has been observed that below 340° no appreciable ring transformation takes place and a temperature of $340-350^{\circ}$ is most suitable for this change.

This ring transformation can be best explained by assuming that during dehydrogenation the fission of the cyclopentane ring takes place along the dotted lines (VII) giving rise to an intermediate which undergoes a dual mode of cyclisation with the production of both anthracene and phenanthrene derivatives.

An alternative view has been advanced by Linstead (*Ann. Rep. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, p. 304) based on retro-pinacolic change during the Clemmensen reduction of the spiro-ketone (I) or during its dehydrogenation with the production of (II). In spite of apparent simplicity of this explana-

tion the issue is not quite clear, because it cannot adequately explain the simultaneous formation of phenanthrene and anthracene during the

dehydrogenation of tetrahydronaphthalene-spiro-cyclopentane (VII ; R=H). Furthermore, on the basis of Linstead's views gem-dialkylated tetralones and keto-phenanthrenes on reduction and dehydrogenation should give di-alkylnaphthalenes and phenanthrenes, which is contrary to experience.

Actually the products isolated were mono-alkylnaphthalenes and phenanthrenes (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1938, 151, 82 ; 1939, 152, 9)

The two spiro-hydrocarbons (VII ; R=Me and R=Et) required for dehydrogenation studies were synthesised in the following manner. The anhydride of cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid condenses with toluene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, with the formation of a keto-acid which must be either (III ; R=Me) or (IV ; R=Me). The keto-acid on reduction by the Clemmensen method gives a γ -tolylbutyric acid, the ethyl ester of which does not condense with ethyl oxalate in presence of potassium ethoxide, indicating absence of hydrogen in the α -carbon atom. The constitution of the tolylbutyric acid should, therefore, be represented by (V ; R=Me) and consequently the keto-acid by (III ; R=Me). It is found that the chloride of the half ester (VIII) (Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2593) reacts with toluene in presence of aluminium chloride giving a keto-ester which on hydrolysis forms a keto-acid identical with (III ; R=Me), instead of the expected acid (IV ; R=Me).

In order to explain this observation a rearrangement of the acid chloride during the Friedel-Craft's reaction has to be assumed.

The keto-acid obtained by the condensation of benzene and the anhydride of *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1934, 11, 392), to which the formula (IV; R=H) was attributed, has now been proved to be $\alpha\alpha$ -*cyclopentane- β -benzoylpropionic acid* (III; R=H).

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

The cyclisation of $\alpha\alpha$ -*cyclopentane- γ -(*p*-tolyl)-butyric acid* (V; R=Me) with 85% sulphuric acid gives the spiro-ketone (VI; R=Me), (*semicarbazone*, m.p. 141-42°) which on reduction according to Clemmensen gives 7-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (VII; R=Me). The latter on dehydrogenation with selenium gives both 3-methylphenanthrene and β -methylanthracene. The formation of 3-methylphenanthrene from the spiro-hydrocarbon (VII; R=Me) lends additional support to the constitution of the keto-acid (III; R=Me). The keto-acid with the alternative structure (IV; R=Me) would have furnished 2-methylphenanthrene and β -methylanthracene as the final products of dehydrogenation.

In a similar manner 7-ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (VII, R=Et) has been synthesised, starting from the anhydride of *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* and ethyl benzene. These two condense in nitrobenzene solution in presence of aluminium chloride giving $\alpha\alpha$ -*cyclopentane- β -(*p*-ethyl)-benzoylpropionic acid* (III; R=Et). The constitution of this keto-acid also follows from the observation that the ethyl ester of $\alpha\alpha$ -*cyclopentane- γ -(*p*-ethyl) phenylbutyric acid* (V; R=Et), obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of the keto acid (III; R=Et) did not form any oxalyl compound. The γ -arylbutyric acid is cyclised with 85% sulphuric acid giving a 76% yield of 1-keto-7-ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spirocyclopentane (VI, R=Et). The spiro-ketone on reduction by the Clemmensen method gives the desired spiro-hydrocarbon (VII; R=Et). This on dehydrogenation with selenium gives 3-ethylphenanthrene and probably β -ethylanthracene. The isolation of these dehydrogenation products further proves the position of the *cyclopentane* ring in the $\alpha\alpha$ -position of the keto-acid (III; R=Et).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

αα-cyclopentane-β-(p-toluoyl)-propionic Acid (III; R = Me).—(a) Aluminium chloride (52 g.) was added to a solution of the anhydride of *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* (30 g.) in dry toluene (100 c.c.) cooled in ice. The mixture was kept at room temperature for 12 hours and warmed at 60–65° for 3 hours. The product was treated with ice and excess of toluene removed in steam. The solid product was purified by extraction with sodium carbonate solution and was crystallised from dilute alcohol in plates, m. p. 149–50°, yield 38 g. (Found : C, 73·4; H, 7·6. $C_{15}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 73·2; H, 7·3 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* of this keto-acid was prepared in aqueous methyl alcoholic solution. It crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 164–65°. (Found : C, 63·5; H, 6·7. $C_{16}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires C, 63·4; H, 6·9 per cent).

(b) Aluminium chloride (18 g.) was added to a solution of the acid chloride of methyl *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetate* (11 g.) in excess of toluene (40 c.c.) cooled in ice. After keeping at the room temperature for 12 hours the mixture was treated with ice, excess of toluene distilled off in steam and the oily product extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with sodium carbonate solution, dried and distilled as a thick oil, b. p. 170–75°/5 mm. (Found : C, 73·6; H, 7·9. $C_{16}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 73·8; H, 7·7 per cent).

It was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash and the resulting keto-acid crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 149–50°.

αα-cyclopentane-γ-(p-tolyl)-butyric Acid (V; R = Me).—*αα-cyclopentane-β-(p-toluoyl)-propionic acid* (15 g.), amalgamated zinc (75 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (75 c.c.) were boiled for 24 hours. The reduced acid was extracted with ether, ether distilled off and the residue was dissolved in warm sodium carbonate solution, filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The separated reduced acid (sticky solid) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure, b. p. 186–90°/5 mm. The liquid distillate readily solidified and was crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. 40–60°) in colourless needles, m. p. 68–69°, yield 10·5 g. (Found : C, 77·6; H, 8·6. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 77·6; H, 8·6 per cent).

The *anilide* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m. p. 124°. (Found: C, 82.0; H, 8.1. $C_{21}H_{15}ON$ requires, C, 82.1; H, 8.1 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by the action of ethyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride. It is a colourless oil, b. p. 160-62°/5 mm. (Found: C, 78.2; H, 9.1. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.5; H, 9.2 per cent).

7-*Methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane* (VI; R = Me).—*α-cyclopentane-γ-(p-tolyl)-butyric acid* (15 g.) was added to 85% sulphuric acid and the mixture heated at 100° for 1½ hours with stirring. The product was poured on ice, extracted with ether, the extract washed with dilute ammonia and water, dried with sodium sulphate and distilled, b. p. 160-63°/5 mm. It possesses a characteristic smell, yield 11 g., i.e., 77% of the theoretical, d_4^{20} , 1.0578; n_D , 1.55583; $[R_L]_D$, 65.0 (calc., 63.5). (Found: C, 83.8; H, 8.5. $C_{15}H_{18}O$ requires C, 84.1; H, 8.4 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was obtained by heating the spiro-ketone with semicarbazide acetate in methyl alcoholic solution for 6 hours. After distilling off the alcohol, the residue was triturated with a little petroleum ether when the semicarbazone was obtained in a crystalline state. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine needles, m. p. 141-42°. (Found: C, 70.8; H, 7.6. $C_{16}H_{21}N_3$ requires C, 70.8; H, 7.7 per cent).

7-*Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:3-spiro-cyclopentane* (VII; R = Me).—The foregoing spiro-ketone (8 g.) was boiled with amalgamated zinc (40 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, washed, dried and distilled, when a colourless liquid (5 g.) came over at 135-36°/6 mm, d_4^{21} , 0.980417; n_D , 1.53856; $[R_L]_D$, 63.86 (calc., 63.47). (Found: C, 89.7; H, 10.2. $C_{15}H_{20}$ requires C, 90.0; H, 10.0 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of 7-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane.—The spiro-hydrocarbon (3 g.) was heated with powdered selenium (6 g.) in a metal-bath at 300-340° for 6 hours and at 340-50° for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, the solvent removed and the residual oil distilled over sodium. At first a liquid fraction (1.5 g.) came over at 140-50°/6 mm. and then a small amount at a higher temperature, solidifying in the side-tube of the distilling flask and exhibit-

ing a bluish fluorescence. The solid fraction was pressed on a porous tile and had m. p. 198-200° and this was probably β -methylantracene. The liquid fraction was warmed with picric acid in alcoholic solution and the separated picrate after recrystallisation from spirit had m. p. 135°. The hydrocarbon was regenerated from the picrate and after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 61-62°. (Found: C, 93.5; H, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{12}$: C, 93.75; H, 6.25 per cent).

The *picrate* prepared from this regenerated hydrocarbon had m. p. 137-38° and the mixed m. p. with the picrate of an authentic sample of 3-methylphenanthrene showed no depression.

aa-cyclopentane- β -(p-ethyl)-benzoylpropionic Acid (III; R = Et):—
 (a) It was prepared from ethyl benzene (25 g.), anhydride of cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (31 g.), carbon disulphide (100 c.c.) and aluminium chloride (52 g.) according to the procedure followed in the case of *aa-cyclopentane- β -(p-toluoyl)-propionic acid*. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. 90-100°) in needles, m. p. 128-29°, yield 38 g. (Found: C, 73.7; H, 7.7. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 73.8; H, 7.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m. p. 130°. (Found: C, 64.1; H, 7.3. $C_{17}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.3 per cent).

(b) The chloride prepared from 5 g. of methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetate and 4 g. of ethylbenzene in 30 c.c. of carbon disulphide were treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (7.5 g.). The product, a keto-ester, was worked in the usual manner and distilled as a thick oil at 195-98°/10 mm, yield 4.9 g. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 8.1. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 74.4; H, 8.0 per cent).

This keto-ester on hydrolysis with alcoholic potash gave an acid which after crystallisation from petroleum ether melted at 128-29° and the mixed m. p. with a sample prepared by method (a) remained undepressed.

aa-cyclopentane- γ -(p-ethyl)-phenylbutyric Acid (V; R = Et).—The foregoing keto-acid (30 g.) was reduced by the Celemmensen method with amalgamated zinc (150 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (150 c.c.). The reduced acid (solid) was first purified by extraction with sodium carbonate solution and finally by distillation at 200-02°/9 mm. This distillate slowly solidified and crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. 30-50°) in thick

needles, m. p. 51-53°, yield 21 g. (Found: C, 77·8; H, 9·0. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78·1; H, 8·9 per cent).

The *anilide* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m. p. 117°. (Found. C, 82·0; H, 8·4. $C_{22}H_{27}ON$ requires C, 82·2; H, 8·4 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by the action of ethyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride. It is a colourless oil, b. p. 144-46°/5 mm. (Found: C, 78·6; H, 9·6. $C_{18}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 78·8; H, 9·5 per cent). Ethyl oxalate did not condense with the ethyl ester in presence of potassium ethoxide.

1-Keto-7-ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (VI; R = Et).— $\alpha\alpha$ -cyclopentane- γ -(*p*-ethyl) phenylbutyric acid (15 g.) was cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid (45 c.c.) and water (15 c.c.) at 100°. The product was a colourless liquid, b.p. 175°/9 mm., yield 10·5 g., $d_4^{28.5}$, 1·04336; n_D , 1·552907; $[R_L]_D$, 69·9. (Found: C, 84·0; H, 8·9. $C_{16}H_{20}O$ requires C, 84·2; H, 8·8 per cent).

7-Ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (VII; R = Et).—The foregoing spiro-ketone (9 g.) was reduced by heating with amalgamated zinc (50 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) for 24 hours. The product distilled at 154-56°/9 mm., yield 7·2 g., $d_4^{27.8}$, 0·96652; n_D , 1·53515; $[R_L]_D$, 68·95. (Found: C, 89·5; H, 10·2. $C_{16}H_{22}$ requires C, 89·7; H, 10·3 per cent).

Selenium Dehydrogenation of 7-Ethyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane.—The spiro-hydrocarbon (4·5 g.) was heated with selenium (5 g.) in a metal-bath at 300-20° for 6 hours and at 340-50° for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether and distilled over sodium under reduced pressure when 1·2 g. of an oily product containing a little crystalline substance was obtained. This was redistilled and the fractions coming at 170-75°/5 mm. and at 175-190°/5 mm. were separately collected.

The first fraction (0·8 g.) was warmed with picric acid (1 g.) in alcoholic solution and the picrate after being freed from oily matter by pressing on a porous tile, was twice recrystallised from spirit in orange needles, m. p. 117-18°. The mixed m. p. with the picrate of 3-ethyl phenanthrene, prepared from 3-phenanthroylmethyl ketone (Haworth and Mavin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1012), was 117-18°. (Found: C, 60·6; H, 4·0. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{17}O_7N_3$: C, 60·7; H, 3·9 per cent). The hydrocarbon regenerated from the picrate (0·5 g.) was distilled over sodium, the distillate (0·18 g.) did not solidify even on cooling. (Found: C, 93·1; H, 6·7. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{14}$: C, 93·2; H, 6·8 per cent).

The second fraction was cooled in ice when colourless shining flakes, m. p. $135-37^{\circ}$, separated. From its high melting nature it seems to be 2-ethylanthracene.

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